

Impact of Banks' Financial, Internal, Social and Environmental Sustainability on Banks' Performance – An Analytical Study

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Abstract

Modern banks, whether public, private or foreign besides achieving financial and internal sustainability have started to finance social and environmental related projects. In addition to economic interest, banks have discerned the fact that without social progress and environmental protection, the growth is incomplete. Alarmed by social inequality and environmental degradation, the country is suffering and concentrating on lop-sided human development.

This research paper analyses and interprets the impact of banks' sustainability in terms of financial, internal, social and environmental sustainability factors on public, private and foreign banks' business performances. Business performance of the sample banks connotes the long-term returns, risk management, new banking products development, increasing market share, reputation, brand value and shareholder value. Integration of social and environmental issues in the businesses improved access to international capital contributing to poverty and unemployment alleviation, environmental protection, social progress in the locality where sample banks function, facilitating the reduction of global warming by financing carbon credit projects and so on.

The present research work presents the business case for sustainable banking by drawing on responses from top-level management (n=20), bank managers (n=4) and banks staff (n=40) in three sectors of 4 banks each - public sector, private sector and foreign banks operating in India in general and Bengaluru in particular. The study used a survey, descriptive, and analytical method of research. The causal relationship between independent and dependent variables have been appropriately aligned. The measurement of sustainability is done through scaling techniques and statistical tools. The qualitative data studied have been quantified using Likert's scale. Based on the results derived from study it can be concluded that the financial, internal, social and environmental sustainability of sample public sector, private sector and foreign banks have profound impact on banks' business performances.

Keywords: Sustainability-Economic, Internal, Social and Environmental, Business Performance.

Introduction

Sustainability means meeting “the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs”. The Banking industry in India has been undergoing evolutionary and revolutionary changes over the years. The 21st-century banking is a significant part of a country’s growth story. The financial vibrancy of a country depends on the effective and meaningful role played by the banking industry of that country. The Bank as a financial intermediary has redefined its way of doing business. The paradigm shift in the structure, technology, people and activities in terms of products and services has brought in new role and responsibilities for the banks operating in India. The banking sector reforms opened up new challenges, issues, opportunities and benefits for the Indian banks and foreign banks operating in India. Sustainable banking is a philosophy that involves everything about banking. It believes in a value system which says a bank’s commercial activities must not only benefit its staff and shareholders, but also its customers and the wider economy, while at the same time preventing, or at least minimizing, any undue effects on society and the natural environment.

Need for the Study

Bank’s Sustainability dimensions serve as a guide for strategic planning for banking institutions that want to improve their competitive advantage by integrating financial, human resources, technological, internal and external, social and environmental sustainability concepts, management systems, products and services into their businesses by public sector, private sector and foreign banks operating in India. There are ample challenges and opportunities on the path of maintaining the sustainability of banks.

The present research paper presents the business case for sustainable banking by drawing on responses from top-level management, bank managers, and bank staff in three categories of banks - public sector, private sector and foreign banks operating in India. It has drawn parameters from International Financial Corporation (IFC) survey reports (2005) including 14 case studies from pioneering financial institutions. The IFC survey collected and analyzed data from more than 120 financial and banking institutions in 43 emerging market countries that had participated in IFCs Competitive Business Advantage training workshops. The results reveal drivers, opportunities, and trends in the banking sector’s response to sustainability. The research paper highlights on the concrete steps to integrate financial, internal, external social and environmental sustainability into their policies, practices, products, and services. The impact of sustainability of banks on the performance and effectiveness is the crux of the thesis

Objectives of the Study

This research paper has two-fold objectives which analyses and interprets the impact of banks’ sustainability;

1. Analyzing the impact of banks’ sustainability on their business performances. Business performance of the sample banks connotes the long-term returns, risk management, new banking products development, increasing market share, reputation, brand value and shareholder value.
2. Analyzing the impact of environmental and social factors on sustainability of sample banks. The impact of macro environmental and social factors on sustainability of sample banks connotes integration of the two issues in the businesses, improved access to international capital contributing to poverty and un-employment alleviation, environmental protection, social progress in the locality where sample banks functions, facilitating the reduction of global warming by financing carbon credit projects.

Review of Literature

The research study reviewed books, articles, reports, journals, magazines and internet based resources on the topic 'Impact of financial, internal, social and environmental sustainability of banks in India – An Analytical Study'. The review comprises of financial, internal, social and environmental sustainability literature of public sector banks, private sector banks and foreign banks.

Olaf Weber (2013)¹ propounds that Banks and other financial institutions can learn from this development that the integration of sustainability issues into policies, strategies, products, and services of the banking industry makes the banking business sense as well. Those institutions that were early adaptors of sustainable banking could avoid financial risks resulting from environmental or social impacts and were able to create business opportunities as well.

Huw Maggs (2014)² contends that Multinational banks can influence transformation of financial system of a country. Banks are at the heart of the contemporary financial system, which underpins both the physiology and psychology of modern business, and that needs to evolve significantly.

K. C. Chakrabarty (2011)³ deputy secretary RBI, in his speech opines that sustainability reporting has become more relevant and important in today's context not only from social or environmental concerns, but because, globally, we have come to realize that our goal is not just growth and profits, but we are looking at inclusive growth.

Deka Bank (2015)⁴ reports that, Deka's mission is to provide all employees with a safe working environment that is built on trust. The intention is to develop the skills of employees as far as possible and put them to use for the benefit of the Bank's overall value-driven strategy, as well as to create working conditions that ensure the long-term physical, and mental wellbeing of our employees. Employees need access to the right environment at every stage of their professional lives to enable them to develop both personally and professionally.

Research Design

i) Type of Research

The study used a survey, descriptive study and analytical method of research

Survey Method: The review of literature identified the topic "Sustainability of Banks in India-An Analytical Study". The independent, dependent and extraneous variables are identified. The objective-wise hypotheses were coined and questionnaire was drafted. The pre-testing of questionnaire strongly directed the study. The data collected from top management branch managers, and bank staff is tabulated, analyzed and interpreted. Based on the analysis and interpretation major findings, conclusion and suggestions are enumerated, discussed and incorporated. It is a fact finding study on the banks' sustainability in regard to sample public sector, private sector and foreign banks.

Descriptive Study: The researcher meticulously portrays the past and the present facts on financial, technological, internal and external, regulatory, infrastructural, customer, and other stakeholders of social and environmental sustainability of three categories of sample banks – public sector, private sector and foreign banks. The study portrays the facts of what is happening on the sustainability fronts of banks under the study at the present scenario.

Analytical Study: The researcher analysed the corporate policy, culture, philosophy, program, vision, mission, goals, and objectives of sample public sector, private sector and foreign banks.

1 Sustainable Banking – History and Current Developments

2 Why finance giants should bank on sustainability.

3 Non-financial Reporting – What, Why and How – Indian Perspective

4 www.dekabank.com

The financial, technical, internal, external sustainability policy and programs of twelve (12) banks, four each in the public sector, private sector, and foreign banks were well analysed. To analyze causal relationship, independent, and dependent variables are appropriately aligned. To measure the sustainability, scaling techniques and statistical tools are used. The qualitative data under the study are quantified by using Likert's scale.

iii) Sampling

• Universe/Population

All the Public sector, Private sector and Foreign banks operating in Karnataka and Maharashtra state, as corporate offices of these banks are located in Mumbai, Pune, Bangalore, and Mangalore .

• Sample units

Categories of Banks:

- Public Sector Banks
- Private Sector Banks
- Foreign Banks

Categories of Respondents:

- Top Management Authorities
- Branch Managers
- Bank Staff

• Sample Size

Composition of Sample Size

S. No	Category of Respondents	Number	Sampling Technique used
1	Sample Banks: Public Sector Banks Private Sector Banks Foreign Banks	04 04 04	Purposive and Judgmental Sampling
2	Sample Respondents: Top Management Authorities (5x4=20x3) Branch Managers (1x4=4x3) Bank Staff (10x4=40x3)	60 12 120	Judgmental Sampling Judgmental Sampling Stratified Random Sampling

• Bases of Sampling

- The Bank should be in existence for a minimum period of 15 years before the collection of data for the study.
- The minimum turnover of the bank should be Rs. 500 crores per annum.
- The Bank must have in place the internal, external, financial, social, and environmental sustainability programmes and practices.

ii) Data Collection

1) Primary Data

The methodology adopted for this research program is survey and descriptive study. Well-structured questionnaires and schedules for sample respondents were prepared, and administered to gather the primary data on the topic from three categories of banks. To elicit further information personal interview of all the three categories of respondents were undertaken.

2) Secondary Data

The secondary data have been gathered from books, articles, reports, international financial and banking institutions, RBI bulletins, newspapers, journals, magazines and web resources.

3) Plan of Analysis and data Interpretation using statistical tools:

The study used a survey, descriptive and analytical methods.

Variables under Impact of Banks’ financial, internal, social and environmental sustainability on Banks’ Performance

S. No	Variables	No. of Items
1	Impact of Banks' Sustainability on its Business Performance	07
2	Impact of Social and Environmental factors on Sustainability of Banks	06
Total		13

Source: Primary Data

Impact of Banks’ Financial, Internal, Social, and Environmental Sustainability on Banks’ Performance

An attempt has been made to know what constitute impact of banks’ financial, internal, social, and environmental sustainability on banks’ performance in three categories of banks under study, the data are tabulated and analysed as follows

Table 1 Impact of Bank’s Sustainability on its Business Performance

S No	Statements	Scale	Responses									Mean Score	S.D
			Public Sector Banks (n=4)			Private Sector Banks (n=4)			Foreign Banks (n=4)				
			TLM (n=20)	BMI (n=4)	BS (n=40)	TLM (n=20)	BMI (n=4)	BS (n=40)	TLM (n=20)	BMI (n=4)	BS (n=40)		
1	Greater and higher long-term returns by financing more sustainable projects and businesses.	TFE	6 (30%)	2 (50%)	16 (40%)	6 (30%)	2 (50%)	16 (40%)	7 (35%)	2 (50%)	16 (40%)	3.9844	1.0459
		TGE	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	15 (37.5%)	7 (35%)	2 (50%)	15 (37.5%)	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	15 (37.5%)		
		TME	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	-	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	-	5 (12.5%)	3 (15%)	-	5 (12.5%)	1 (5%)	-	4 (10%)		
		NTL	3 (15%)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-		

2	Reduced risk	TFE	5 (25%)	-	11 (27.5%)	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	2 (10%)	-	8 (20%)	3.1302	1.3762
		TGE	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)		
		TSE	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		NTL	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
3	New business development through new products and services	TFE	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	16 (40%)	3.0833	1.4805
		TGE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	14 (35%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	1 (5%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	2 (5%)		
		NTL	7 (35%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)	7 (35%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	2 (10%)	-	3 (7.5%)		
4	Increased market share in sustainability-driven sectors	TFE	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	5 (25%)	-	10 (25%)	4 (20%)	-	10 (25%)	3.1563	1.4018
		TGE	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)		
		TME	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)		
		TSE	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		NTL	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
5	Enhanced reputation and better brand value	TFE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	14 (35%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)	3.5417	1.2400
		TGE	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	15 (37.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	13 (32.5%)	5 (12.5%)	1 (25%)	14 (35%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)		
		TSE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	2 (5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	2 (5%)		
		NTL	2 (10%)	-	3 (7.5%)	2 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	2 (10%)	-	2 (5%)		
6	Better access to capital from international financial organizations.	TFE	2 (10%)	-	1 (2.5%)	3 (15%)	-	2 (5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	2.4583	1.4113
		TGE	2 (10%)	-	3 (7.5%)	4 (20%)	-	6 (15%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		NTL	9 (45%)	2 (50%)	21 (52.5%)	6 (30%)	2 (50%)	21 (52.5%)	3 (15%)	-	9 (22.5%)		

7	Increased value to shareholders.	TFE	2 (10%)	-	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	-	7 (17.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	2.7760	1.4853
		TGE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)		
		TME	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
		TSE	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)		
		NTL	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	17 (42.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	14 (35%)	4 (20%)	-	11 (27.5%)		
Mean Score			2.8357	2.9286	3.1000	3.1500	2.8214	3.0714	3.2500	3.1786	3.4924		
Standard. Deviation			1.4915	1.3313	1.4825	1.3830	1.3346	1.4720	1.3256	1.2786	1.3573		

(Source: Primary Data) [Key: TFE :To full extent, TGE: To a great extent, TME: To a moderate extent, TSE: To a small extent, NTL: Not at all.] [TLM= Top Level Management, BM= Branch Managers, BS=Bank Staff]

• Analysis and Interpretation

The main impact of sample banks' sustainability is that it contributed to greater and higher long-term financial returns. This was possible on account of extending loans and advances to the sustainable projects and businesses. This fact was emphasized by the top level management respondents in public sector (60%), private sector (65%) and foreign banks (75%). The averages mean score stand at 3.9844 and the corresponding standard deviation is fixed at 1.0459. As far branch managers in three sample sectors concerned 75 percent (n=4), 100 percent (n=4) and 75 percent (n=4) respectively of public sector, private sector and foreign banks under the study have endorsed the same. In so far as the bank staff of the concerned sample banks' branches are concerned, similar view was expressed by them (see table -1)

The aim of sustainability of the sample banks in all the three sectors is concerned is to manage the risk and accordingly reduce the bank specific micro and macro environmental variable risks. The average mean score for the statement is 3.1302 and the standard deviation is 1.3762. The Sustainability is possible for the banks under the study only when they concentrate on new products and services development in order to meet the ever changing requirements of the customers, both individual and corporate (mean score 3.0833 and standard deviation 1.4805).

The stimulus for sample banks' sustainability is to increase the market share, reputation, brand value, shareholder value and better access to capital from international financial organisations. These five parameters impact significantly vary from sector to sector. Therefore the mean score variation ranges from 2.4583 to 3.5417. The standard deviation ranges from 1.2400 to 2.7760. The reason for variations are on account of government control in case of public sector, board autonomy and flexibility in case private sector and foreign banks.

• Conclusion

It can be concluded that sample banks internal, external and financial sustainability influenced their business performances considerably (see table -1). Further, the impact can be seen on the dependent variables of the study. They are long-term returns, reduced risk, new business development through new products and services, increased market share, reputation, brand value, shareholder value, and access to capital from international financial institutions. The responses are well captured in table -1.

Table-2 Impact of Social and Environmental factors on Sustainability of Banks

S No	Statements	Scale	Responses									Mean Score	S.D
			Public Sector Banks (n=4)			Private Sector Banks (n=4)			Foreign Banks (n=4)				
			TLM (n=20)	BM (n=4)	BS (n=40)	TLM (n=20)	BM (n=4)	BS (n=40)	TLM (n=20)	BM (n=4)	BS (n=40)		
1	The business case for sustainable banking is strong. There are positive changes as a result of steps taken by the banks to integrate social and environmental issues in their business.	TFE	4 (20%)	-	5 (12.5%)	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	3 (15%)	-	5 (12.5%)	2.7135	1.4458
		TGE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		NTL	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	16 (40%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	15 (37.5%)		
2	The integration of sustainability into management systems and practices brings tangible benefits, including new lines of business, new clients, greater access to financing, greater shareholder value, and improved reputation and goodwill.	TFE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	3.3333	1.3394
		TGE	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	13 (32.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		TME	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		TSE	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)		
		NTL	4 (20%)	-	4 (10%)	2 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	2 (10%)	-	9 (22.5%)		
3	There is a reduction in risk as a result of considering social and environmental issues by the Commercial banks by virtue of sustainability practice	TFE	3 (15%)	-	8 (20%)	2 (10%)	-	7 (17.5%)	2 (10%)	-	6 (15%)	2.7604	1.4173
		TGE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	-	9 (22.5%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	3 (7.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	2 (50%)	3 (7.5%)		
		NTL	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	3 (7.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	18 (45%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)		
4	The bank's sustainability practice brought about improved access to international capital, improved brand value and reputation, new business, and improved community relations.	TFE	2 (10%)	-	1 (2.5%)	3 (15%)	-	2 (5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	2.4583	1.4173
		TGE	2 (10%)	-	3 (7.5%)	4 (20%)	-	6 (15%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	11 (27.5%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	7 (17.5%)		
		TSE	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	9 (22.5%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	5 (12.5%)		
		NTL	9 (45%)	2 (50%)	21 (52.5%)	6 (30%)	2 (50%)	21 (52.5%)	3 (15%)	-	9 (22.5%)		

5	Improved access to international capital contributing to poverty and un-employment alleviation, environmental protection, social progress in the locality where sample banks functions.	TFE	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	3 (15%)	1 (25%)	6 (15%)	2 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	3.2448	1.2226
		TGE	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	16 (40%)	5 (25%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		TME	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	16 (40%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)		
		TSE	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		NTL	1 (5%)	-	2 (5%)	2 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
6	Improved access to international capital for sample banks paved way for the reduction of global warming by financing carbon credit projects	TFE	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	2 (10%)	-	4 (10%)	6 (30%)	2 (50%)	14 (35%)	3.0463	1.1940
		TGE	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	12 (30%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	14 (35%)		
		TME	8 (40%)	1 (25%)	15 (38%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	6 (30%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)		
		TSE	2 (10%)	1 (25%)	3 (8%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	10 (25%)	-	-	4 (10%)		
		NTL	-	-	2 (5%)	4 (20%)	1 (25%)	8 (20%)	-	-	-		
Mean Score		3.1412	2.7083	3.0250	3.1417	2.7083	2.8583	3.1417	3.0417	3.0125			
Standard Deviation		1.3860	1.2676	1.3051	1.3860	1.2676	1.4277	1.3860	1.3015	1.4333			

(Source: Primary Data) [Key: TFE : To full extent, TGE: To a great extent, TME: To a moderate extent, TSE: To a small extent, NTL: Not at all.] [TLM= Top Level Management, BM= Branch Managers, BS=Bank Staff]

• Analysis and Interpretation

Modern banks - public, private or foreign have started to finance social and environmental related projects. This segment immensely contributes to the bank sustainability. In addition to economic interest, banks have discerned the fact that without social progress, and environmental protection, the growth is incomplete. Alarmed by social inequality, and environmental degradation, the country is suffering and concentrating on lop-sided human development. The international financial corporation in its survey and study (2012) covering 46 countries of the globe highlighted the fact that the present banking system must integrate social and environmental management system in to overall business strategy of the banks. In this connection the impact of environmental and social factors on the sustainability of sample banks assumes relevance.

The study enumerated six parameters concerning the impact of environmental and social factors on the sustainability of sample banks (see table 2).

The sustainability of banks at present is strong. There are positive changes as a result of steps taken by the banks to integrate social and environmental issues. The integration varies from sector to sector under the study. It is moderately pronounced in sample public sector banks. With respect to private and foreign banks the integration is still emerging and evolving. Therefore, the responses reveal moderate mean score (2.7135, n=12) and greater variation reflected through standard deviation(1.4458) (see table 2).

The integration of environmental and social management systems into business strategy of sample banks lead to tangible benefits including new lines of business, new clients, greater access to financing, greater shareholder value, improved reputation and goodwill for all the twelve banks under the study (mean score 3.3333 and standard deviation 1.3394).

There is a reduction in risk as a result of considering social, and the environmental issues by the sample banks in three sectors. Not all three banks reduced their total risks on account of the inclusion of lending towards the projects concerning social and environmental ones. They have other mechanisms to mitigate the risks. The funding of social, and environmental projects to a great extent reduces the non-performing assets risks (mean score 2.7604 and SD 1.4380).

The sample banks that are into environmental and social projects gained access to capital from international financial institutions improved their brand value and reputation, new business and community relations across the globe (mean score 2.4583 and SD 1.4173).

Improved access to foreign capital, the sample banks especially public and private banks wielded their funds to social, and environmental projects in India. This helped to reduce social inequality and to increase environmental protection progress. Banks the public sector banks in study were channelized the government scheme funds for poverty and unemployment alleviation, amelioration of rural poor, and sectional including social imbalance. Further, the global warming issue has been mitigated to some extent by providing loans and advances to carbon credit trading and ventures by the sample banks under the study (mean score 3.0463 and SD 1.1940).

• Conclusion

Thus, financial, internal, social, and the environmental sustainability of sample public sector, private sector and foreign banks have profound impact on banks' business performances and social and environmental issues (see table-2).

Inferential Statistical Results

To corroborate the descriptive facts and figures evidenced by mean scores and standard deviation scores applicable to the given statements under four constructs namely financial, internal, external and environmental sustainability of sample public, private and foreign banks, the inferential evidences have been fortified by using parametric and non-parametric statistical tools such as Cross-correlation, chi-square and factor analysis. The internal consistency of questions contained in each construct is verified on the basis of Cronbach's Alpha results. The detailed results are as follows:

Impact of Financial Sustainability on Banks' Performance

Table 3 Cross Correlation Values of Sample Banks' Business Performance – Dependent Variables

Variables	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7
X1	1	.867**	.839**	.884**	.895**	.718**	.823**
		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
X2	.867**	1	.843**	.931**	.922**	.785**	.885**
	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
X3	.839**	.843**	1	.892**	.859**	.865**	.894**
	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000
X4	.884**	.931**	.892**	1	.900**	.828**	.925**
	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000
X5	.895**	.922**	.859**	.900**	1	.737**	.839**
	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000
X6	.718**	.785**	.865**	.828**	.737**	1	.897**
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000

X7	.823**	.885**	.894**	.925**	.839**	.897**	1
	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Key to Variables

X1 = Greater and higher long-term returns by financing more sustainable projects and businesses..

X2 = Reduced risk

X3 = New business development through new products and services

X4 = Increased market share in sustainability-driven sectors

X5 = Enhanced reputation and better brand value

X6 = Better access to capital from international financial organizations.

X7 = Increased value to shareholders.

The inter-correlation results indicate that among seven independent variables, five of them were wielded significant influence on the five dependent variables forming sample banks business performance. Linking of Aadhar card to customers bank account for Direct Benefit Transfer, use of internal technology such as note counting machines, computers, printers and currency checking machine, reduction of cost per transaction, technological up-gradation and maintenance of the servers influenced significantly the increased market share in sustainability driven factors, increased shareholder values, better access to capital from international financial organizations and followed by new business development through innovative products and services and reduction of risk. Thus, the causal relationship between the parameters of technological sustainability and business performance of the sample banks under the study is statistically analysed and proved (see table 3).

The KMO and Bartlett's results of eleven items are given below

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.936
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1032.039
	df	66
	Sig.	.000

For a degree of freedom 66 at 5 percent level of significance, the table values are 85.965. The calculated values are 1032.039. Since the calculated values are greater than the table values, hence null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis is that there exists a strong and positive relationship between technological intervention and branch business performance of banks in sample public, private and foreign banks.

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